

Isolation and Characterisation of Methyl-(α -chloro- β -3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylate

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A byproduct of Darzens condensation has been isolated and characterised by U.V., I.R., NMR and Mass spectrometric and analytical methods which indicate that the new compound is methyl-(α -chloro- β -3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylate and that the Darzens condensation is essentially similar to Aldol condensation.

DURING the attempts to prepare homopiperonal from piperonal according to the procedure of Yoshio and Takeshi¹, Darzens glycidic ester condensation of piperonal with methyl chloroacetate in presence of methanolic sodium methoxide was conducted. In this connection the author wishes to report that a byproduct compound having m.p. 136° has been isolated in nearly 50% yield along with the expected product, methyl 3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-glycidate, having m.p. 64°. The byproduct compound was shown to be methyl-(α -chloro- β -3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-acrylate by analytical and spectroscopic methods.

It is a general belief^{2,3} that a Darzens condensation occurs via Aldol addition intermediates. The communication of isolation of two intermediate chlorohydrins by Ballester and Perez-Blanco⁴ was the first evidence in this respect ruling out the "bivalent radical mechanism". Of course, it is assumed that the first two steps of the oxirane-yielding base-catalysed reaction of a carbonyl compound and a halogenomethylene substance, are fundamentally identical with those of an Aldol condensation. As in the Aldol condensation the intermediate halogenohydrine anion of Darzens condensation may pick up a proton from the medium and give the halogenohydrine. To complete the analogy, another reaction, occurring also in the Aldol condensation, i.e., elimination of hydroxyl ion from halogenohydrine intermediate and consequent formation of an ethylene compound was shown by Jorlander⁵ and Claisen⁶. The present result of isolation and characterisation of the above mentioned byproduct substantiates the analogy and is also a clear evidence to show that the Aldol and the Darzens condensations are not only formally but also essentially similar.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Kofler hot stage m.p. apparatus. Micro-chemical analysis for chlorine was done by oxygen flask method. U.V. spectrum

was taken on Beckman DB-G (double beam recording mode) grating spectrophotometer. I.R. was taken on Unicam SPI000 infra red spectrophotometer. NMR was recorded on Varian A-60 NMR-spectrophotometer (Tetramethyl silane as internal reference). Mass spectrum was taken on A.E.I. Mass spectrometer, Model MS 9.

A solution of 54.0 g. (1.8 mols) of piperonal and 47.4 ml. (2.7 mols) of methyl chloroacetate were slowly added (during a period of 3 hr) under stirring to 12.42 g. (2.7 gram-atoms) sodium in 180 ml. dry methanol chilled to -10° in an ice-salt bath. After the addition of the mixture the stirring was continued for 2 hr at -5° and then left overnight at room temperature (17°). The mixture was poured into 700 ml. ice-water containing 4 ml. acetic acid. The separated white crystalline powder, methyl 3-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl) glycidate was collected by filtration, washed with cold water and dried in a vacuum dessicator, yield 90%. The crude glycidate when subjected to melting point determination, was noted to consist of two types of substances. The crude dry powder was then dissolved by boiling with a large volume of petroleum ether (b.p. range 60-80) over the steam bath. The clear solution was decanted and on cooling inside a refrigerator overnight it deposited distinctly two kinds of colourless crystals—one lumpy crystalline solids mostly at the bottom of the flask and the other in bunches of flaky needles adhering to the sides. They were manually separated easily in pure state. The lumpy solid epoxy ester melted at 64° (lit. m.p. 65°). (Found: C, 59.50; H, 3.61%; Calc. for C₁₁H₁₀O₃, C, 59.45; H, 3.50%.)

The byproduct flaky needles melted at 136°. On recrystallising from benzene in colourless needles, the melting point did not change. Yield 49.2%. The compound responded to Beilstein test for chlorine. Found: C, 54.91; H, 3.86; Cl, 14.65%; C₁₁H₉O₄Cl requires C, 54.88; H, 3.74; Cl, 14.76%. U.V. $\lambda_{max}^{Ethanol}$ 210 nm ($\epsilon = 46,901$); 297 nm ($\epsilon = 32,727$); 329 nm ($\epsilon = 40,363$). I.R. ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1730 cm⁻¹ (S)

(ester carbonyl) 1610 cm^{-1} (M) (aromatic C = C). NMR (CDCl_3) 3.85δ singlet (3H), (COOCH_3); 6.00δ singlet (2H) (-O. CH_2 -O-); 6.83δ doublet (1H) aromatic proton ($J = 8.5$ cps/ortho); 7.30δ doublet (1H) aromatic proton ($J = 8.5$ cps/ortho); 7.53δ singlet (1H) aromatic proton; 7.80δ singlet (1H) vinylic proton.

Mass spectrum : The mass spectrum of the compound ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$) displayed the characteristic abundance ratio of M and M^{+2} peaks in 3 : 1, corresponding to Cl^{35} and Cl^{37} . M-35 and M-36 peaks were also observed due to loss of Cl and HCl from the molecular ion. Prominent fragments occurred at m/e 242 (M^{+2} , 30%), 240 (M^+ , Base peak), 209 (M^+ -HCl, 15%), 181 (M^+ - COOCH_3 , 6%); 179 (M^+ - HCOOCH_3 , 10%); 146 (M^+ - COOCH_3 , -Cl, 20%). Strong metastable peak at m/e 173.5 was associated with the fragmentation $240 \rightarrow 209$ (173.5).

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